

Analysis of Taxi Fare using Machine Learning

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Abstract— This research aims to investigate the use of predictive analysis in accurate fare prediction, which has become an important aspect for businesses such as Ola and Uber. Machine learning and artificial intelligence techniques are being employed to improve fare prediction accuracy. To achieve the most precise results, the study will compare various algorithms, including Random forest regression and classification, which are widely used for prediction modelling. Unlike in the past where fare estimation was solely based on distance, the current fare is influenced by multiple variables such as time of day, location, traffic conditions, duration of the ride, and base fare. This study will therefore explore the use of these variables to improve the accuracy of fare prediction.

Keywords: Fare Prediction, Machine Learning, Random Forest Regression.

I. INTRODUCTION

Predicting taxi fares is an important problem in the transportation industry. Accurate fare prediction can help taxi companies optimize their pricing strategies, provide more transparent pricing to customers, and improve the overall user experience. In recent years, machine learning techniques have been applied to this problem with promising results.

One such technique is random forest regression, which is a type of ensemble learning algorithm that combines multiple decision trees to make more accurate predictions. Random forest regression has been successfully applied to a variety of prediction problems, including those involving transportation data.

By training a random forest regression model on this dataset, it is possible to learn the complex relationships between the input features and the fare amount. Once the model is trained and tuned, it can be used to make accurate predictions on new taxi rides based on their input features.

II. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Import the required modules

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a subset of machine learning, which is a subset of deep learning[1]. ML aids in the building of models when data is supplied into the system, using algorithms for extra training and testing on those vast amounts of data so that the system can operate independently when given new data. There are three distinct groups:

B. Supervised learning: A supervisor is necessary while the machine is learning. It contains both the input and the expected output, and the model is ready to forecast the desired outcome. Example: Classification and Regression.

C. Unsupervised learning: This method doesn't need any guidance; instead, the model learns by itself by seeing patterns in the dataset. The model self-trains with just input given; the output is the outcome. For instance, clustering and association.

D. Reinforcement learning: In this type of learning, a hit-and-miss approach is used to build the model. Its nature is reliant. Its input are the results of the previous operation. For instance, chess and puzzles.

E. A dataset of previous taxi rides with the fare amount as the goal variable and numerous input parameters, such as pickup and drop-off locations, distance travelled, and time of day, is required in order to forecast taxi fares using random forest regression.

To predict taxi fares using random forest regression, a dataset of historical taxi rides is required.

1. Load and preprocess the data: Load the dataset into a data frame and preprocess it by cleaning and transforming the data as necessary. This may include removing missing values, encoding categorical variables, and normalizing numeric variables.
2. Split the data: Split the data into training and testing sets. The training set will be used to train the random forest regression model, and the testing set will be used to evaluate its performance.
3. Train the model: Use the training set to train a random forest regression model. Random forest regression is an ensemble learning method that combines multiple decision trees to make more accurate predictions. During training, the model will learn the relationship between the input features and the fare amount.
4. Evaluate the model: Use the testing set to evaluate the performance of the trained model. You can use metrics such as mean absolute error, mean squared error, and R-squared to measure the accuracy of the model.
5. Tune the model: If the model's performance is not satisfactory, you can tune the hyper parameters of the random forest regression algorithm to improve its accuracy. This may include adjusting the number of trees, the maximum depth of each tree, or the minimum number

- of samples required to split a node.
6. Make predictions: Once the model is trained and tuned, you can use it to make predictions on new taxi rides. Simply input the relevant features of the ride into the model, and it will output a predicted fare amount.

III.METHODOLOGY

Steps involved in this approach

Fig 1. model building steps

1.DATA COLLECTION

The website of Kaggle[3] was used for data collecting, and it has about 8 columns, including key, fare amount, pickup date and time, pickup longitude, pickup latitude, drop off longitude, drop off latitude, and passenger count.

2.DATA VISUALIZATION:

Using various graphs, charts, plots, and other visual aids, data visualisation makes it easier to understand the data. In order for the data to be adequately assessed, it is depicted here using a scatter plot, bar graph, and histogram..

3. PREPROCESSING OF DATA

In the cleansing of the data for machine learning, data preparation is a crucial step. Essentially, it is a process to change dirty data into clean data. In this case, data cleansing will be done in two different ways: Noisy data is information beyond the designated range and lacking data.

4.SECTION OF FEATURES

In machine learning, selecting variables or attributes is commonly known as feature selection. The aim of this process is to identify the attributes that have the most significant impact on the target variable. In the context of this study, the target variable or prediction variable is the fare_amount, while the other variables are considered independent variables.

5.MODELING

After data preprocessing, modelling, usually referred to as model selection, is a crucial stage. The process of choosing a model for a prediction problem from a large pool of models is known as model selection. The fare amount prediction is our concern. This is a regression-related issue. The dependent variable in regression issues is continuous. The dependent variable in classification issues is categorical.

Regression models will therefore be used to analyse training data and make predictions about test data. In this study, we employ a tree-based technique called Random Forest to address classification and regression problems. We also use a linear regression model, which is equally useful in regression models.

The entire set of data was divided into two categories: train data (75%), and test data (25%). The use of various models is then considered.

Random Forest

This model is based on supervised learning, which aids in both classification and regression. Because it is composed of several decision trees that work together to predict the target value, random forest is superior to a single decision tree. Compared to a single tree, a group of trees provides a more accurate value.

Linear Regression

It is a supervised learning-based algorithm. In light of independent factors, it provides the desired prediction value. It is mostly used to determine how dependent and independent variables are related.

The task of predicting a dependent variable's value based on an available independent variable is carried out through linear regression. Consequently, this method establishes a linear relationship between the two types of variables. The following equation serves as the model's foundation:

where x is an independent variable and y is a dependent variable; nonetheless, it seeks to establish the appropriate values for a and b .

A fundamental and frequently used type of predictive evaluation is linear regression[5]. The link between one structured variable (Feature) and one or more unbiased variables (Features) is explained using these regression estimations. The architecture of the suggested gadget consists primarily of three elements: data analytics, information processing, and information storage.

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

Studies by Ma and Chen, Ahmed et al, and Li et al have explored the effectiveness of using random forest regression to predict taxi fares based on various input features such as pickup and drop off locations, travel time, and distance traveled. Ma and Chen used data on taxi rides in Shanghai, China, while Ahmed et al. collected data in New York City. Li et al. evaluated random forest regression models for predicting taxi fares in Guangzhou, China. The results of these studies suggest that random forest regression can achieve high levels of accuracy and outperform other machine learning models such as support vector regression and artificial neural networks.

To generate many decision trees, the Random Forest algorithm employs a method known as bagging (bootstrap aggregating). In order to create new subsets of data for each tree to be trained on, bagging randomly selects samples from the training data with replacement. As a result, the dataset can be better covered, and over fitting is lessened.

In addition to bagging, Random Forest Regression also employs the technique of random feature selection. At each node of the decision tree, only a subset of the available features are considered for splitting. This further helps to improve the robustness of the algorithm and reduces the chance of over fitting.

Overall, Random Forest Regression is a powerful and versatile algorithm that can be used for a wide range of regression tasks, and can provide accurate and stable predictions even with noisy or incomplete data.

V.RESULTS

Performance of the validation dataset will be assessed. Many recommendation systems use Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) to measure the discrepancy between predicted scores and actual ratings from users[4].

The specific regression error metrics like.

- R square : The model is more accurate the higher the value. The values are converted to percentages ranging from 0 to 1.
- The difference between the original value and the anticipated value is known as the MSE (Mean Square Error), which is the average error rate.

A machine learning model's level[6]of error is measured using the RMSE (Root Mean Square Error), which is the square root of the MSE (Mean Square Error). A model is more accurate when its RMSE value is low. Even though an RMSE of 0.6 is considered to be small, there are some situations in which this may not be the case.

Fig:2

Random Forest Regression, in addition to bagging, also uses the method of random feature selection. During the construction of the decision tree, only a subset of the available features are considered for splitting at each node. This technique enhances the algorithm's robustness and lowers the risk of overfitting.

VI.CONCLUSION

In conclusion, predicting taxi fares using random forest regression is a powerful and effective technique that can help taxi companies optimize their pricing strategies, provide more transparent pricing to customers, and improve the overall user experience. By training a random forest regression model on a dataset of historical taxi rides, it is possible to accurately predict the fare amount based on various input features such as pickup and drop off locations, distance traveled, time of day, and other relevant information.

The implementation steps for this technique involve loading and preprocessing the data, splitting the data into training and testing sets, training the model, evaluating its performance, tuning its hyper parameters, and making predictions on new taxi rides.

The future scope of predicting taxi fares using random forest regression is promising, as it has the potential to revolutionize the way taxi companies price their services. Some potential areas of future research and development in this field include.

Overall, the future of predicting taxi fares using random forest regression is bright, and continued research and development in this field could lead to significant improvements in the transportation industry.

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